

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AND FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS OF FIBER COMPOSITES UNDER IMPACT LOADING

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Longitudinal and off-axis compression tests for orthogonal and uni-directional fiber composites (cloth F.R.P. and roving F.R.P.) have been conducted by means of the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar method. The effect of fiber orientation on the strength under impact loading was investigated. Further, the high speed impact test where the cylindrical F.R.P. specimen collided against a steel rod anvil was also conducted using an air gun in order to study fracture characteristics of these composites under very high speed impact.

The experimental results are summarized as follows. Both strengths of longitudinal and off-axis composites increase with an increase in strain rate. Hill's criterion can be approximately applied to the off-axis strength also under impact loading. Shear bands and fiber breaks are found for the cloth F.R.P.. On the other hand, no fiber break occurs in any case and inter-laminar fracture between fibers and resins, or fracture in resin layers are found for the roving F.R.P..

INTRODUCTION

Some characteristics of fiber reinforced composites under impact loading have been investigated. Among them the energy absorption or the toughness measured by the Charpy, the Izod and the drop weight tests is often studied [1]. However, the energy does not give the direct explanation for the general dynamic fracture behavior of fiber composites because of the complexity in the fracture process through the tests. Even today, simple characteristics, for instance strength properties in tension and compression should be given under impact loading as well as under static loading.

This paper presents the effect of the fiber orientation angle to the loading direction on the compressive strength properties under impact loading for orthogonal and uni-directional fiber composites. The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar method (shortly the Hopkinson bar method) was used for the impact test. However, the specimen is not compressed instantaneously by the Hopkinson bar method. It is compressed gradually by reflections of the stress wave at both ends of the specimen during 50-200 μ sec. In order to know fracture characteristics at more high rate of loading than in the Hopkinson bar test, the high speed impact test was conducted using an air gun.

TEST SPECIMEN

The test specimen consists of a polyester resin as a matrix and glass fibers as reinforcements. The plain glass cloth (MG-252) was used as a reinforcement for the orthogonally reinforced composite (called cloth F.R.P.). The glass roving (WR-740N) was used for the uni-directionally reinforced composite (called roving F.R.P.).

Uni-directional fiber sheets were made by pull-out of the weft of the roving glass cloth. First, laminates were made by means of the hand lay-up method at room temperature for 24 hours and then cured for 4 hours at 80°C. After curing they were cut in the longitudinal and off-axis direction, and machined into 10mm in diameter (d) and 15mm long (1) as shown in Fig.1 for the conventional compression test. For the high speed impact test, three sizes of the specimen were used (shown in Fig.2). The fiber orientation angle θ to the loading direction were 0, 22.5 and 45° for the cloth F.R.P., and 0, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90° for the roving F.R.P. (see Fig.3).

Fig.1 Dimensions of the specimen for conventional compression tests

Fig.2 Dimensions of the specimen for high speed impact tests

Fig.3 Fiber orientation angle θ to the loading direction

APPARATUS AND TEST PROCEDURE

All tests were carried out at room temperature. The Hopkinson bar assembly shown in Fig.4 was used for the impact test. Data were processed by a computer to obtain stress-strain curves. In order to obtain the effect of strain rate on the compressive fracture properties, the compression test at static strain rate was also conducted by an Instron type testing machine. For the static and quasi-static tests cross-head speeds were 5 and 500mm/min, respectively. The end surfaces of the specimen were lubricated with a grease to minimize the friction.

Fig.4 Hopkinson pressure bar apparatus

Fig.5 Air gun assembly

For the high speed impact test, an air gun shown in Fig.5 was used. Test specimens were propelled with high speeds and they collided against a steel rod anvil on which strain gages were mounted. The resultant stress wave transmitted into this rod can be measured and then the maximum load caused by the impact between the specimen and the rod is obtained. The stress applied to the specimen is converted as

follows:

$$\text{stress} = \frac{\text{load measured by the steel rod strain}}{\text{cross sectional area of the specimen}} \quad (1)$$

Impact fracture behaviors during the test were also observed by high speed photographs using a micro-flash.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Conventional compression test -

Fig.6 shows typical S-S curves of the longitudinal cloth F.R.P. under static and impact loading. Fig.7 also shows typical S-S curves of the off-axis cloth F.R.P. under impact loading. The off-axis cloth F.R.P. has a large nonlinearity in the stress-strain relation even under impact loading. The effect of glass content on the compressive strength of the longitudinal cloth F.R.P. is shown in Fig.8. The curves show the average results of 5 samples in each test. For the impact test, the nominal strain rate (about 500-600) denotes the maximum strain rate during compression in each test. As for the specimen having any glass content, each value as to the mechanical properties obtained under impact loading is higher than that obtained under static loading. However, each effect of glass content on each mechanical property under impact loading is different. Under impact loading the strength has a peak at about 35% V_f , but there is no peak of the strength under static loading. The effect of glass content on the energy to break is similar to that on the compressive strength although about 31% V_f has the peak. The same tendency observed in the compressive strength of cloth F.R.P. is reported by Nevill et. al [2] in their study for the steel wire reinforced epoxy.

Fig.6 Typical stress-strain curves of the cloth F.R.P.; $\theta=0^\circ$, $V_f=30.5\%$

Fig.8 Compressive strength vs. glass content; cloth F.R.P.

Fig.7 Typical S-S curves of the cloth F.R.P. under impact loading; $V_f=36.4\%$

Fig.9 shows the effect of strain rate on the compressive strength. The strengths of both the longitudinal and the off-axis specimens increase as the strain rate increases. The increasing rate of the strength against the strain rate for the longitudinal F.R.P. is a little larger than that for the off-axis F.R.P.. Fig.10 shows the effect of the fiber orientation angle on the compressive strength at each strain rate. The results calculated by the Hill's criterion [3] are also presented in this figure. The detail for the Hill's criterion is later given in the results of the roving F.R.P.. Although the shear strength at each strain rate is necessary to calculate the off-axis strength, it is not given from the present experiment. Suitable values for the shear strengths which approximately satisfied the experimental results were used as the shear strength to calculate the Hill's criterion.

Fig.9 Effect of strain rate on compressive strength of cloth F.R.P.

Fig.10 Compressive strength vs. fiber orientation angle ; cloth F.R.P., $V_f=36.4\%$

Photo.1 shows the instantaneous photograph at the instant of the impact fracture of the cloth F.R.P. in the Hopkinson bar test using the micro-flash. From the shear band across the laminae (oblique crack) and fiber breaks are found. Photo.2 shows the failed specimens having different fiber orientation angles of the cloth F.R.P.. The final fracture of any kinds of the specimens was accompanied with the shear band regardless of the difference of the fiber orientation angle and strain

Photo.1 Micro-flash photographs of cloth F.R.P. under impact loading

Photo.2 Failed specimens ; cloth F.R.P., $V_f=36.4\%$

rate. For the specimen of $\theta=0^\circ$ the surface of it except the vicinity of the shear band did not whiten, but the white part of the specimen is found according to the increase of the off-axis degree. Especially all surface of the specimen of $\theta=45^\circ$ whitened. It is already known that this whitening for the off-axis cloth F.R.P. begins considerably at earlier stage before the fracture occurs. The same fracture mode as this is observed on the 90° cross-ply F.R.P., which is reinforced by the same number of glass fiber warps and woofs, but not woven like the plain woven glass cloth. Further, the shear band occurs in case of the dumb'bell type specimen of the cloth F.R.P.. This phenomenon is not the distinguished phenomenon which depends upon the configuration of the specimen. From these observations, it is defined that on the laminated F.R.P. like the cloth F.R.P., the resin permeates into the interstices of the glass yarns of the cloth and consequently the glass cloth behaves as the plate which responds nonlinearly to the compressive load in case of having the off-axis angle, then the final fracture of the cloth F.R.P. is caused by the buckling of this reinforced plate. Since the direction of the glass fiber in the plate does not coincide with the load direction for the off-axis F.R.P., the glass cloth in the plate (=lamina) deforms easily in plane by the in-plane shear stress. The observed rigidity in the loading direction is rather low, and the specimen is considerably shortened before the buckling of the plate occurs. As the result, the delamination takes place in the laminae.

Photo.3 Failed specimen of cross-ply F.R.P.

Fig.11 shows typical S-S curves of the roving F.R.P.. Fig.12 shows that the strength of the roving F.R.P. also increases as the strain rate increases. It is considered that the similar increase in strength is considerably derived from the dependence of the rate sensitivity of the resin. This dependence affects the success of Hill's criterion at high strain rate. The effect of the fiber orientation angle on the compressive strength under static, quasi-static and impact loading is shown in Fig.13.

Fig.11 Typical S-S curves of the roving F.R.P. under impact loading

Fig.12 Effect of strain rate on compressive strength of the roving F.R.P.

Hill's fracture criterion which gives the strength of anisotropic composites is represented by the following equation.

$$\frac{1}{F_{\theta}^2} = \frac{\cos^4 \theta}{F_L^2} + \left(\frac{1}{F_{LT}^2} - \frac{1}{F_T^2} \right) \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{F_T^2} \quad (2)$$

Where F_{θ} is an off-axis strength of the composites whose fiber orientation angle is θ . F_L and F_T are the longitudinal ($\theta=0^\circ$) and transverse ($\theta=90^\circ$) compressive strengths, respectively. F_{LT} is the in-plane shear strength, but it is too difficult to measure it directly. In Fig.13, solid lines were calculated using Eq.(2), where suitable values of the shear strengths F_{LT} approximately satisfied the experimental results at each strain rate were found by try and error calculations as well as in case of the cloth F.R.P.. At any strain rate the compressive strength decreases rapidly as the fiber orientation angle increases up to $\theta=30^\circ$. After it becomes the minimum value at $\theta=45^\circ$, the strength increases slightly. These experimental results reveal that the Hill's criterion could be applied to the strength of the uni-directional fiber composites not only under static loading but also under impact loading. However, Hill's criterion can not give the fracture mode of fiber composites. While the maximum stress theory gives the fracture mode. From this theory, it is predicted that the final fracture is caused by the shear stress parallel to the fiber (which is the inter-laminar shear stress and not the in-plane shear stress) from $\theta=5^\circ$ to 45° , and at ranges over 45° to 90° it is caused by the transverse shear stress perpendicular to the fiber, which exists in the oblique plane across the laminae.

Fig.13 Compressive strength vs. fiber orientation angle ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=27.1\%$

Photo.4 Failed specimens ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=27.1\%$

Photo.4 shows the failed specimens of the roving F.R.P.. The observed direction of the fracture surface of the specimen whose fiber orientation angle is the same is constant even though the strain rate changes. Two cases can be considered with respect to the shear fracture (caused by the shear stress). One is the matrix fracture which occurs in the matrix. Another is the delamination in the interface between the matrix and the fiber. The directions of the fracture surfaces coincide with the max-

imum stress theory as shown in Photo.4. Longitudinal cleavages along the fibers were found for the longitudinal specimen ($\theta=0^\circ$). It is considered that the fracture for the longitudinal F.R.P. was initiated by the fiber buckling because the compressive strength was lower than the tensile strength. The aspect of the failed specimen also suggests the fiber buckling of the extension mode. It is noted that no fiber breaks occur through all tests for the uni-directional fiber composite dissimilar to the case of the cloth F.R.P. where the shear band across the laminae and fiber breaks were found.

-High speed impact test-

Fig.14 shows the stress-time records of the polyester (60mm long) specimen. Fig.15 shows the relation between the maximum stress applied to the specimen at the collision between the specimen and the steel anvil, and the incident velocity. The test results arranged on two broken lines with the intersection of two lines $V_i=100$ m/sec. The effect of the length of the specimen is not found. A swelling at the head of the stress wave is small under $V_i=100$ m/sec as shown in Fig.14 and the stress wave measured resembles the trapwzoidal wave expected by the theory of the one dimensional elastic wave.

Fig.14 Stress-time records ; polyester

V_c ; critical incident velocity
 σ_c ; critical maximum stress

Fig.15 Maximum stress vs. incident velocity ; polyester

Now, the case when the polyester collides with the anvil elastically is considered. Since the impacted surface between the specimen and the anvil has the same particle velocity V^* , the stress σ_a in the steel rod anvil and the stress σ_s in the specimen are given as follows.

$$\sigma_s = \frac{A_a \cdot \rho_a \cdot C_a \cdot \rho_s \cdot C_s}{(A_a \cdot \rho_a \cdot C_a + A_s \cdot \rho_s \cdot C_s)} \cdot V_s \quad (3)$$

Where

V_s ; Incident velocity of the specimen
 ρ_a ; Density of the anvil
 ρ_s ; Density of the specimen
 C_a ; Elastic wave velocity in the anvil
 C_s ; Elastic wave velocity in the specimen
 A_a ; Cross-sectional area of the anvil
 A_s ; Cross-sectional area of the specimen

The dashed line in Fig.15 shows the calculated results by Eq.(3) using following values.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_a &= 7800 \text{ kg/mm}^3, & A_a &= 113.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2, & C_a &= 5137 \text{ m/sec} \\ \rho_s &= 1210 \text{ kg/mm}^3, & A_s &= 78.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2, & C_s &= 2000 \text{ m/sec} \end{aligned}$$

The measured trapezoidal stress waves represent the dashed line (round symbols in the figure). The dashed line shows the stress value obtained by the elastic collision of the specimen against the anvil. From the relation between the elastic wave velocity and the Young's modulus, the dynamic Young's modulus of the polyester is calculated as $E=48.4$ (MPa). When the incident velocity exceeds 100 m/sec, the concave part at the head of the stress wave appears nearly at $t=9$ μsec progresses gradually, and the line representing the relation between the maximum stress and the incident velocity transfers from the dashed line to the solid line. On this time, the very high stress is applied to the end of the specimen at instant of the collision. Soon after the collision, the local fracture as shown in Photo.5 occurs in the vicinity of the specimen because of such high stress. The time duration after the collision to the fracture which means the time duration to reach the maximum stress is at most about 5 μsec . Therefore, if the elastic wave velocity in the polyester is supposed to be 2 mm/ μsec , the compressive stress wave propagates only 10 mm in the specimen away from the impacted end till the time when the fracture takes place. This fact affirms that the length of the specimen does not affect on its maximum stress (which is regarded as the fracture strength in this case) in the high speed impact test.

The dashed line in Fig.15 also shows that the relation between the compressive stress and the strain of the polyester under impact loading is linear until the 2.16 MPa, where the incident velocity $V_c=100$ m/sec. This fact coincides with the test result of the polyester by the Hopkinson bar test.

Photo.5 Micro-flash photographs ;
polyester, $\times 10 \times 30$

Fig.16 shows the stress-time records of the longitudinal cloth F.R.P.. At low incident velocities, the stress wave shows the trapezoidal shape similar to the case

Fig.16 Stress-time records ; cloth F.R.P., $V_f=30.5\%$, $\theta=0^\circ$, $\rho 10 \times 60$

Photo.6 Micro-flash photographs ; longitudinal cloth F.R.P. $V_f=30.5\%$, $\rho 10 \times 30$

of the polyester. The maximum stress also increases according to the increase of the incident velocity, but there is no swelling like the polyester. After the stress becomes maximum, it decreases rapidly. The shape of the stress wave becomes similar to each other at high speeds as well as in case of the polyester, although the length of the specimen is different. The relation between the maximum stress of the cloth F.R.P. and the incident velocity is also represented by two broken lines. The broken point of both straight lines is 83 m/sec and 3.6 MPa. It is supposed that the maximum stress corresponds to the compressive strength under impact loading measured by the Hopkinson bar method. However, even in case that the incident velocity was $V_i=59$ m/sec and the observed maximum stress was lower than 3.6 MPa, the specimen was broken obviously. In this case its maximum stress was only 2.3 MPa and this value is a little higher than the static strength, but rather low value compared to the impact strength measured by the Hopkinson bar method. This fact recognizes that the change of the stress during short period after the collision is very important for the study on the compressive impact strength of F.R.P..

On the above example, although the low stress which is a little higher than the static strength is applied to the cloth F.R.P. specimen and the risetime of the stress is very short as $7 \sim 8 \mu\text{sec}$, the specimen is broken if such stress is maintained constantly for more than $20 \mu\text{sec}$. As for the Hopkinson bar method, it takes about $100 \mu\text{sec}$ until the fracture occurs. The stress applied to the specimen increases gradually and at last the fracture occurs.

Photo.6 shows the photographs at the instant of the collision. Under 200 m/sec incident velocity, the crack like a V shape took place at first and after then the final fracture was progressed by the wedge effect of this crack. This V shape occurs across the laminae similar to the shear band in case of the conventional compression test. From the photograph observations, it is supposed that the initial fracture mode at the early stage is also the shear mode. Fig.17 shows the effect of glass content on the maximum stress at each incident velocity. The maximum stress increases with the increase of the incident velocity, but in these curves, the peak points appear in the vicinity of $V_f=35\%$. This characteristic is similar to the case of the Hopkinson test results for the cloth F.R.P..

Fig.18 shows the stress wave records of the 45° off-axis cloth F.R.P.. The shape of the stress wave is very similar to the case of the polyester. After the initial peak the deep hollow in the stress wave is observed. As for the specimen of $\theta=22.5^\circ$, the second peak in the stress wave disappears at more than $V_i=108$ m/sec. The stress decreased gradually after it reached its maximum value as well as in case of the longitudinal F.R.P..

Fig.17 Maximum stress vs. glass content ; cloth F.R.P.

Photo.7 shows the instant of the high speed collision of the off-axis cloth F.R.P.. Similar shear bands are also found. This fact shows that the fracture mode for the off-axis cloth F.R.P. is about the same as in the conventional compression test.

Fig.18 Stress-time records ; cloth F.R.P., $V_f=36.4\%$, $\theta=45^\circ$, $\times 10 \times 30$

Photo.7 Micro-flash photographs ; off-axis cloth F.R.P., $V_f=36.4\%$, $\times 10 \times 30$

The effect of the fiber orientation angle on the maximum stress at various incident velocity is shown in Fig.19. Dissimilarly to the results of the impact test using the Hopkinson bar method, it is apparent that Hill's criterion can not be applied as for the high speed impact fracture.

Fig.20 shows the stress-time records for the longitudinal roving F.R.P.. At low incident velocities ($V_i=47, 60$ m/sec), $\times 10 \times 60$ mm specimens were not broken and the resultant stress wave profiles also had trapezoidal shapes. For the longitudinal specimen, the V shape cracks or any shear bands did not occur as shown in Photo.8. No fiber break also occurred. It is found also in the relation between the maximum

Fig.19 Maximum stress vs. fiber orientation angle; cloth F.R.P., $V_f=36.4\%$

Fig.20 Stress-time records; roving F.R.P., $V_f=30.3\%$, $\theta=0^\circ$

Photo.8 Micro-flash photographs; longitudinal roving F.R.P. $\phi 10 \times 30$

stress and the incident velocity that the maximum stress which is not affected by the length of the specimen increases linearly as the incident velocity increases until the critical velocity V_c . The critical incident velocity and the critical maximum stress for the longitudinal roving F.R.P. are about 90m/sec and 5.3 MPa, respectively. This stress is also approximately equal to the impact compressive strength measured by the Hopkinson bar method. The first line extended from the origin also corresponds with the assumption of the elastic collision between the specimen and the anvil, where the dynamic Young's modulus calculated using this first line is $E=233$ MPa. This value coincides with the dynamic Young's modulus measured by the elastic wave velocity experiment. Some 60mm long specimens were broken under the critical velocity similarly to the case of the longitudinal cloth F.R.P.. It is supposed that as under the critical velocity the specimen collides against the anvil elastically, the specimen is not broken. In fact, for the specimen of 30mm long, the fracture is not

estimated from the stress wave profile and the apparent fracture did not occur except the slight damage at the impacted end. It is also shows that the duration of the high stress level is the key point to understand the impact fracture. For the specimen of 30mm long, the stress caused by the collision is canceled by the unloading wave reflected at the free end of the specimen earlier than for the specimen of 60mm long since the specimen of 30mm long is shorter than the specimen of 60mm long. The stress duration for the specimen of 30mm long is a half of that of 60mm long although the stress level is the same as in case of the specimen of 60mm long.

Fig. 21 Stress-time records ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=30.3\%$

Fig. 22 Stress-time records ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=30.3\%$

Fig. 23 Maximum stress vs. incident velocity ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=30.3\%$

Fig. 24 Maximum stress vs. fiber orientation angle ; roving F.R.P., $V_f=30.3\%$

Fig.21 and 22 also show the stress-time records of the off-axis roving F.R.P.. The maximum stress decreases as the fiber orientation angle increases. Simultaneously, the stress wave profile also changed. Aswelling occurs at near $\theta=45^\circ$ and a small second peak is found. This swelling vanishes at $\theta=90^\circ$. It is different from the other cases (the polyester and the cloth F.R.P.) that the second peak is very low. The effect of the fiber orientation angle on the compressive strength at any strain rates in the ranges between $\theta=30^\circ$ and 90° obtained by the conventional compression test, is little as shown in Fig.12. On the other hand, in case of the high impact test, the effect of the fiber orientation angle on the maximum stress becomes larger than as shown in Fig.23 and 24. The increasing rate of the maximum stress to the incident velocity for the 90° off-axis specimen is larger than that for other off-axis specimen. It seems that the maximum stress of the 90° off-axis specimen becomes the same as the maximum stress of the 15° off-axis specimen at higher incident velocity.

Photo.9 shows the instant of the collision of the off-axis roving F.R.P.. Also in this case, no fiber break occurred and observed fracture behaviors from Photo.9 can be corresponded to the results shown in Photo.4.

Photo.9 Micro-flash photographs ;
off-axis roving F.R.P.
#10x60

CONCLUSION

The experimental results on the orthogonal and the uni-directional fiber composites are summarized as follows;

1. Compressive strengths of both longitudinal and off-axis F.R.P. increase as the strain rate increases. Under impact loading, however, Hill's criterion can be approximately applied to predict the off-axis compressive strength. Fracture mode of the off-axis F.R.P. were coincided with the maximum stress theory. Oblique cracks (shear bands) across the laminae and fiber breaks occurred for the cloth F.R.P.. On the other hand, no fiber break occurred for the roving F.R.P..

2. The observed stress caused in the anvil by the collision decreased rapidly when the specimen was broken. The effect of the fiber orientation angle on the observed stress waves was also found. Oblique cracks (shear bands) and fiber breaks were also found for the cloth F.R.P., but no fiber break occurred for the roving F.R.P.. Relations between the incident velocity and the maximum stress were given by two broken lines even including the polyester. These relations were not affected by the length of the specimen. The first line extended from the origin represents the state of the elastic collision between the specimen and the steel rod anvil. The slope of the second line was lower than that of the first line.

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